

Synthesis of Furano Compounds: Part XXXV. Synthesis of Some Phenanthro-Naphthofurans

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A synthesis of the oxygen heterohelicene (I) and the isomeric naphtho-phenanthrofuran (IV) are described. Experiments on the resolution of the former have been so far unsuccessful. Their spectral properties have been studied.

Although phenanthrenes carrying substituents at the 4 and 5 positions are under considerable steric strain, at least two such compounds, had been prepared and characterised till 1940¹. Synthesis of phenanthro(3, 4-C)phenanthrene (I) (also named hexahelicene)² was reported in 1956 and its resolution into optical antipodes was possible on account of its helical structure. It was expected that the replacement of a benzene ring by a furan ring might produce a similar helical structure and such a compound, as (II), would be expected to exhibit properties arising from molecular overcrowding. An account of synthesis of (II) and related compounds is given below :

Friedel-Crafts reaction of 1-naphthoyl chloride with 2-methoxynaphthalene afforded the phenol (IV). The related phenoxy ester (V) was hydrolysed to the acid (VI) and then cyclised with sodium acetate-acetic anhydride to (VII). Alternatively the ester (V) was cyclised to (VIII) by sodium methoxide in methanol, an ester exchange having taken place during the reaction. Hydrolysis of the ester followed by decarboxylation gave (VII). The structure of (VII) was also unequivocally proved by its independent synthesis from the naphthoxy ketone (XII) by cyclodehydration with phosphoric anhydride in benzene. The coumarone (VII) on formylation gave the 2-aldehyde (X) the orientation of the formyl group proved by oxidation to the acid (IX). The aldehyde was converted into the pyruvic acid (XI) by the hydrolysis of the related azlactone. The keto-acid on cyclodehydration gave (III) which on

1. M. S. Newman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 2295.
2. (a) M. S. Newman and D. Lednicer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4765. (b) A simple synthesis of hepta-helicene has been reported, R. H. Martin, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967(8), 743. (c) Synthesis, resolution and optical rotatory dispersion of sulphur hexa- and hepta-heterohelicenes have now been reported, H. Wynberg and M. B. Groen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5334.

decarboxylation gave naphtho(4, 5 : 1'', 2'')(3', 4' : 2, 3) phenanthro furan (II), a heterocyclic analogue of hexahelicene, in cream coloured plates, m.p. 253°.

The compound exhibited violet fluorescence in organic solvents. It did not give a picrate or trinitrobenzene complex or a trinitrofluorenone complex. The inability of (II) to form complexes may be interpreted to signify that it has a nonplanar structure³—a property also exhibited by hexahelicene. It may be noted that an alternative cyclisation of (XI) may be expected at the other *peri* position to give the pleiadiene (XIII). But this structure is rejected on the ground that all the pleiadienes are strongly coloured⁴ and, moreover, *peri* cyclisation requires the presence of appropriate activating substituents⁵. The mass spectrum of (II) gives the correct molecular weight (m/e 318). There are only some minor fragment ions (M—H, M—2H and M—CH₃) and the corresponding double charged ions in the mass region 140-160, which are characteristic of highly aromatic systems, but give no information about special structural assignments.

The resolution of (II) by complex formation with (–) α -(2, 4, 5, 7)-tetranitro-9-fluoronylidene aminoxy propionic acid (T.A.P.A.), as employed by Newman in the resolution of hexahelicene, was attempted. This reagent, as with (I), did not afford a crystalline complex but gave a deep brown solution. On careful addition of ethanol, a yellowish material (presumably optically rich) was precipitated. The solid was again treated with T.A.P.A. and the process repeated but polarimetric examination of the product obtained in this process did not reveal any optical activity. It is possible that the substance racemised quickly, it has not been possible to ascertain any mutarotation which may be anticipated in cases of resolution of easily racemisable compounds⁶.

The u.v. absorption spectrum of (II) is similar to the isomeric naphthophenanthro furan (XIV) which was also synthesised. The notable feature is that (II) absorbs at lower

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- V. Bockelheide, W. E. Langeland and C. T. Liu, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 2432; V. Bockelheide and G. K. Vick, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 653.
- L. F. Fieser and M. A. Peters, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4347.
- F. Beu_ and D. H. Waring, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2689.

intensity which might indicate significant steric inhibition of resonance in (II). The compound gave characteristic a picrate and a T.N.B. complex. The synthesis of (XIV) started from (XV) along the same sequence (*vide* Experimental) of reactions illustrated before.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

1-(1'-Naphthoyl)-2-naphthol : To a cooled mixture of 2-methoxynaphthalene (4.0 g) and 1-naphthoyl chloride (4.8 g.) in dry carbon disulphide (25 ml.) was added with shaking, finely powdered aluminium chloride (3.4 g.). The mixture immediately developed deep red colour and copious hydrogen chloride was evolved. After the initial reactions subsided, the mixture was gently refluxed over water bath for 6-7 hrs. Carbon disulphide was then distilled out as much as possible and the residue decomposed with ice water and hydrochloric acid and the last traces of solvent removed by steam distillation. The residual yellowish brown lumpy mass deposited yellow needles (6.5 g.) of 1-(1'-naphthoyl)-2-naphthol from ethanol m.p. 114-16°. The compound dissolves in warm sodium hydroxide solution. (Found : C, 84.30; H, 4.60. $C_{21}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 84.54; H, 4.73 %).

Ethyl 1-(1'-naphthoyl)-2-naphthoxyacetate (V) : A solution of the naphthol (12 g.) in dry acetone (150 ml.) was gently refluxed under dry conditions with ethyl bromoacetate (6.6 g.) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (20 g.) for 8 hr. The hot solution was filtered. The ester (V) separated as hard cream coloured crystals, m.p. 109-10°; yield 14.6 g. (Found : C, 78.0; H, 5.2. $C_{25}H_{20}O_4$ requires : C, 78.11; H, 5.24 %).

Methyl 3-(1'-naphthyl)-4 : 5-benzocoumarone-2-carboxylate (VIII) : The aforesaid ester (23.2 g.) was added to a solution of sodium methoxide (from sodium, 1.4 g and dry methanol, 300 ml.) and heated on steam bath for 2 hr. with exclusion of moisture. During this period some of the cyclised product separated as a white solid. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the cyclised product obtained in a pure state (m.p. 171-2°) in quantitative yield. The substance was identified as (VIII) by the determination of m.p. and mixed m.p. with methyl ester prepared by action of methanol-sulphuric acid on the pure acid. (Found : C, 81.7; H, 4.6. $C_{24}H_{16}O_3$ requires : C, 81.8; H, 4.58 %).

3-(1'-Naphthyl)-4 : 5-benzocoumarone-2-carboxylic acid (IX) : The above ester (VIII; 29.2 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing on water bath with alcohol (180 ml.), water (120 ml.) and caustic potash (22 g.) On working up, the acid (IX; 27 g.) obtained, was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 247° (decomp.). (Found : C, 81.0; H, 4.2. $C_{23}H_{14}O_3$ requires : C, 81.64; 4.17 %).

The acid chloride obtained by the action of thionyl chloride on the acid melts at 183°.

3-(1'-Naphthyl)-4 : 5-benzocoumarone (VII) : A mixture of the crude acid (IX; 2 g.), quinoline (17 ml.) and copper bronze (0.8 g.) was boiled gently for 4½ hr. The cooled mass was distinctly acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed twice with sodium carbonate soln. (10%) and once with water. On removal of solvent the coumarone (VII) was obtained as a viscous liquid (0.9 g.) which solidified after a long time as ill-defined, cubical, colourless crystals, m.p. 104°. (Found : C, 89.7; H, 5.0. C₂₂H₁₄O requires : C, 89.77; H, 4.79%).

It gives an orange-red picrate, m.p. 118-20°. (Found : N, 8.13. C₂₈H₁₇O₈N₃ requires : N, 8.03%).

Hydrolysis of Ethyl 1-(1'-naphthoyl)-2-naphthoxyacetate : The ester (V; 30 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing on water bath with alcoholic caustic soda. On working up, a semi-solid mass separated which crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles (23 g.), m.p. 165°. (Found : C, 77.30; H, 4.6. C₂₃H₁₆O₄ requires : C, 77.51; H, 4.53%).

A mixture of the above acid (2.5 g.), acetic anhydride (30 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (4 g.) was refluxed for 1½ hr. The cooled mixture was poured on crushed ice and the solution basified with caustic soda solution. On isolation the furan (2 g.) was obtained as a viscous residue which solidified, m.p. 103-4°; (picrate, orange red needles, m.p. 118-20°). Melting points were not depressed on admixture with samples obtained in experiments described earlier.

α-(2'-Naphthoxy)-1-acetylnaphthalene (XII) : A mixture of 2-naphthol (6 g.) and ω-bromo-1-acetylnaphthalene (10 g) in dry acetone (100 ml.), was refluxed for 5 hr. in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (27 g.). Distillation of acetone gave (XII) as brown viscous mass, which on addition of little alcohol yielded the ketone (3.5 g.) in a crystalline form. Recrystallisation from a small volume of acetic acid gave the pure product, m.p. 106°, as shining yellowish leaflets. (Found : C, 84.10; H, 5.20. C₂₂H₁₆O₂ requires : C, 84.59; H, 5.16%).

Cyclisation : The above ketone (1.9 g.) was dissolved in benzene (50 ml.), phosphorus pentoxide (6 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 16 hr. The cooled mixture was decomposed with iced water and the mixture repeatedly extracted with ether. The ether solution gave (VII; 1.7 g.) containing some persistent impurity. The picrate melted at 118-20°, undepressed on admixture with authentic specimen described earlier.

2-Formyl-3-(1'-naphthyl)-4, 5-benzocoumarone (X) : To a cooled mixture of (VII; 2 g.) and N, N-dimethylformamide (2 g.) was added phosphorus oxychloride (1.5 g.) and the mixture heated on steam bath for 4 hr. The resultant viscous mass was treated with cold water and basified with caustic soda solution. The aldehyde (X; 2 g.) was crystallised from acetic acid in shining, prismatic crystals, m.p. 174°. (Found : C, 85.0; H, 4.40. C₂₃H₁₄O₂ requires : C, 85.70; H, 4.38%). The azlactone was prepared by heating a mixture of the aldehyde (9.6 g.), hippuric acid (6.5 g.), fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 ml.) on steam bath for 30 min. The cooled mixture was decomposed as usual and the crude azlactone (14 g.) was crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles, m.p. 287°. It gives beautiful violet colouration with conc. sulphuric acid. (Found : N, 3.3. C₃₂H₁₉O₃N requires : N, 3.01%).

3-(1'-Naphthyl)-4,5-benzocoumarone-2-pyruvic acid (XI): The foregoing azlactone (1.5 g.) was refluxed for 15 hr. with sodium hydroxide soln. (30 ml.; 10%) and ethanol (15 ml.). Most of the alcohol was removed, the residue diluted with water (20 ml.) and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. A brown lumpy mass was obtained which gave positive ferric reaction. Two crystallisations from acetic acid, gave α -ketonic acid (XI; 0.5 g.) as yellowish-brown crystals, m.p. 235° (decomp.). (Found: C, 78.60; H, 4.50. $C_{25}H_{16}O_4$ requires: C, 78.93; H, 4.24%).

Cyclisation: A solution of the α -ketonic acid (XI; 3.5 g.) in acetic acid (35 ml.) was gently refluxed for 12 hr. with hydrobromic acid (5. ml.; 48%). The cyclised acid (III) separated as a solid on cooling was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow brown needles, m.p. 289-90°. (Found: C, 82.60; H, 4.00. $C_{25}H_{14}O_3$ requires: C, 82.86; H, 3.89%).

Decarboxylation: The crude acid (III; 3.5 g.) was mixed with calcium oxide (10 g.) and carefully heated. The decarboxylated product (II) collected as a solid in the colder part of the apparatus. This was removed and chromatographed over alumina (benzene). The residue after removal of benzene was crystallised from acetic acid, in light yellow woolly needles (1.4 g.), m.p. 253°. (Found: C, 91.00; H, 4.60. $C_{24}H_{14}O$ requires: C, 90.54; H, 4.43%). λ_{max}^{alc} 234, 276, 300, 313, 338, 349, 364 and 384 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.72, 4.35, 4.25, 4.27, 3.89, 4.09, 4.06 and 4.07 respectively).

The substance is very sparingly soluble in ethanol, and sparingly soluble in benzene, acetic acid, chloroform etc. It shows a marked violet fluorescence in very dilute solutions.

It did not form a picrate and did not form a complex with 1, 3, 5-trinitrobenzene. With trinitrofluorenone in benzene, a deep brown solution was obtained, but the complex did not separate.

Experiments on Resolution: To a mixture of the furan (II; 0.48 g.) and (-) α -(2, 4, 5, 7-tetranitrofluorenylaminoxy)-propionic acid (henceforth called T.A.P.A.) (kindly supplied by Prof. M. S. Newman) (0.24 g.) (1/2 equivalent), both pale yellow, was added dry 'Analar' benzene (50 ml.). On little warming clear deep brown solution was obtained. The solution was covered and allowed to stand in the dark. Very little yellow solid deposited within 24 hr. Pure ethanol (15 ml.) was added and after 24 hr. the yellow solid (0.18 g.) was collected.

The furan, obtained after the first stage (0.18) was again mixed with (0.09 g.) of (-)-T.A.P.A. in benzene (8 ml.) and a brown solution obtained by heating. On cooling yellow crystals were deposited (0.19 g.). A few of these crystals were washed with sodium carbonate solution, dried and melting point determined. The bulk of the substance melted at 252-3° (i.e. at the m.p. of the starting material) and a small part of the liquid remained sticking to the capillary at an angle.

The second crop of the furan (0.1 g.) was again treated similarly with half-equivalent of T.A.P.A. (50 mg) and crystals collected after 48 hr. These crystals were dissolved in benzene and the solution filtered through a short alumina column. The filtrate did not show

optical activity. The filtrate was concentrated (to 10 ml.) and again no optical activity could be observed.

The mother liquors containing the complex were brown in colour and light transmission through columns of these solutions was almost nil. So mutarotation, if any, could not be observed.

The processes for attempted resolution were also carried out at the room temp. (20-25°) using different amounts of pure ethanol for the purpose of precipitation but without success.

The final crop of the furan, melted and remelted at the same temp.

α-(2'-Naphthoxy)-2-acetylnaphthalene : A mixture of 2-naphthol (5.8 g.) and *ω*-bromo-2-acetylnaphthalene (9.7 g.) is dry acetone (100 ml.), was refluxed for 5 hr. in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (20 g.). On working up, an oily residue was obtained which on scratching deposited a crystalline solid. Recrystallisation from a moderately large volume of ethanol gave a fairly pure sample of the ketone (9.7 g.), m.p. 126°. (Found : C, 84.0; H, 5.2. C₂₂H₁₆O₂ requires : C, 84.59; H, 5.16%).

The ketone readily gave 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallising as orange needles from ethyl acetate, m.p. 251° (decomp.). (Found : N, 11.50. C₂₈H₂₀O₅N₄ requires : N, 11.38%)

3-(2'-Naphthyl)-4,5-benzocoumarone (XV) : The above ketone (2 g.) was dissolved in benzene (30 ml.) and mixed with phosphorus pentoxide (6 g.) and refluxed for 16 hr. The mixture was worked up in the usual manner. A viscous liquid (1.9 g.) was obtained, which did not deposit crystals from ethanol, benzene and acetic acid. The compound gave a *picrate* in benzene, which crystallised from benzene in orange-red needles, m.p. 149-50°. (Found : N, 8.30. C₂₈H₁₇O₃N₃ requires : N, 8.03%).

1-(2'-Naphthoyl)-2-naphthol : This was obtained by Friedel-Crafts reaction of 2-naphthoyl chloride (19.1 g) with 2-methoxynaphthalene (15.8 g.) in dry carbon disulphide (90 ml.) with anhydrous aluminium chloride (19 g.). The mixture was heated on water bath and decomposed as before. The crude *naphthol*, crystallised from ethanol, in yellow needles, m.p. 144-7°. The pure ketone melts at 156.5°. (Found : C, 84.40, H, 4.92. C₂₁H₁₄O₂ requires : C, 84.54; H, 4.73 %).

The compound gives a positive ferric reaction (blue-black) and a reddish sodium salt. The salt is very slightly soluble in water.

Ethyl 1-(2'-naphthoyl)-2-naphthoxyacetate : A solution of the above crude phenol (3.5 g.) in dry acetone (30 ml.) was refluxed for 7 hr. with ethyl bromoacetate (1.9 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.), and worked up in the usual manner. The *naphthoxy acetate* was obtained as an oil which did not crystallise.

1-(2'-Naphthoyl)-2-naphthoxyacetic Acid : A solution of the above crude ester in ethanol (25 ml.) was heated on water bath with sodium hydroxide solution (30 ml.; 10%) for 2 hr. and worked up in the usual manner. The *acid* (3.8 g.) was repeatedly crystallised from small volumes of acetic acid as faint yellow cluster of needles, m.p. 172°. The acid crystallised very slowly. (Found : C, 77.40; H, 4.50. C₂₃H₁₆O₄ requires C, 77.51; H, 4.53%).

3-(2'-*Naphthyl*)-4, 5-benzocoumarone : A mixture of the foregoing acid (3 g.), acetic anhydride (25 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (6 g.) was slowly refluxed for 1½ hr. The acetic anhydride was decomposed with iced water and the mixture extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed twice with dil. alkali (KOH) and twice with water. Removal of solvent from the dried ether solution gave the *uran* as an oil.

The oil formed an orange-red picrate, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the picrate obtained by the first procedure was 149-50°.

This coumarone was formylated as before with N, N-dimethylformamide to give 2-formyl-3-(2'-naphthyl)-4, 5-benzocoumarone, m.p. 131-40° (80%). As it was found difficult to purify the compound, this was not analysed. The 2, 4-dinitro-*phenylhydrazone* crystallised in red needles, m.p. 295°. (Found : N, 10.90. C₂₉H₂₈O₅N₄ requires : N, 10.93%).

The *azlactone* crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 299°. (Found : N, 3.30. C₃₂H₁₉O₃N requires : N, 3.01%).

3-(2'-*Naphthyl*)-4, 5-benzocoumarone-2-pyruvic Acid : The above *azlactone* (0.8 g.) was refluxed with ethanol (25 ml.) and potassium hydroxide (15 ml.; 10%) for 24 hr. The hot soln. was filtered and left overnight. The gummy mass that deposited was thoroughly washed with warm water and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The semi-solid mass was washed again with warm water and crystallised from acetic acid, 205-6°; yield, 0.25 g. Three more recrystallisations afforded an analytically pure sample of the α -ketonic acid, m.p. 236°. It gives a positive ferric reaction. (Found : C, 78.50; H, 4.60. C₂₅H₁₆O₄ requires : C, 78.93; H, 4.24%).

4, 5 : 1", 2"-*Naphtho*-1', 2' : 3, 2-*phenanthro*furan : A solution of the α -ketonic acid (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (25 ml.) was gently refluxed for 12 hr. with hydrobromic acid (4 ml.; 48%). The hot soln. was filtered and cooled to give cream coloured needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 122-4°. The substance is insoluble in hot and cold alkali. Three recrystallisations from acetic acid afforded a pure sample, m.p. 139°. The substance shows pronounced blue fluorescence in acetic acid. (Found : C, 91.1; H, 4.5. C₂₄H₁₄O requires : C, 90.54; H, 4.43%). λ_{max}^{alc} 231, 252, 268, 297, 311, 340, 356 and 364 m μ (log ϵ , 5.64, 5.43, 5.53, 5.20, 5.23, 5.33, 5.38 and 5.24 respectively). The substance yields a chocolate *picrate* in acetone, m.p. 152-3°. The picrate is not very stable, but the trinitrobenzene complex separated as orange crystals, m.p. 168°. (Found : N, 8.10. C₃₀H₁₇O₇N₃ requires : N, 7.91%).

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